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Catalyzing Energy Balance: A Comparative Analysis of Optimization Algorithms in the DAI Framework

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Abstract—Renewable energy sources (RESs) such as solar panels and wind turbines are increasingly utilized due to their small ecological footprints. However, their inconsistent power generation results in variations in both power supply and grid stability. Integrating RESs in power grids with AI-driven control systems allows for real-time monitoring and control of the electricity grid. This enables more responsive and adaptive grid management, reducing the impact of imbalances caused by sudden changes in demand or supply. This research proposes utilizing a Distributed AI (DAI) framework to ensure energy balance between supply and demand. DAI agents would be placed on each power device for real-time monitoring and control. In this paper, the performance comparison considering the execution time of two optimization techniques, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Linear Programming (LP), is investigated considering energy balancing constraints. The simulation results illustrate the effectiveness of both optimization techniques considering the increased number of power devices.

Index Terms—Distributed AI, power fluctuations, distributed energy resources, power/energy balance, power flow control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the unpredictability of power generation and consumption, the power imbalance is a challenging problem. This scenario is further complicated by evolving Energy Storage Systems (ESSs), which undergo charging and discharging cycles and adapt to different power sources and loads. Managing power systems that rely on these variable renewable sources requires advanced control methods. Consequently, the power system requires new strategies for managing and operating electricity to preserve an equilibrium between changing power supply and demand patterns. While AI has been developed for various aspects of power systems, most solutions remain isolated within centralized systems. Effective communication, quick decision-making, and supportive power control methods for distributed sources are essential, making a distributed AI approach crucial for enhanced stability and safety [1]. This paper explores the efficacy of optimization algorithms like Linear Programming (LP) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) within the DAI framework, contributing to more efficient power management strategies.

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II. BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE AND RELATED WORK

A. Description of Power System

This subsection shows the details of the proposed power system, consisting of power generators (PG), power loads (PL), storage systems (PS), and power flows (i.e., connections) between them. All power-generating and consuming devices are categorized into controllable (PG^c/PL^c) and fluctuating (PG^f/PL^f). The controllable devices can control their power supply/demand with embedded controller. However, the power supply/demand of fluctuating devices cannot be controlled.

B. DAI Framework

This research marks a significant advancement in energy balancing by introducing a novel DAI framework designed for a power system consisting of power generators, loads, and storage systems, enhancing the integration and stability of renewable energy sources. Central to this framework are Belief-Desire-Intention Extended (BDIx) agents, equipped with AI/ML capabilities, enable intelligent and autonomous decision-making for optimal energy distribution and grid stability. Each power device (i.e., generator, load, and storage system) is equipped with a BDIx agent, supplementing these devices with power sensing, power data transmitting, and power control functionalities as shown in [2].

C. Energy Balancing Constraints

The following energy balancing conditions must be satisfied to guarantee the existence of a feasible solution given as,

Condition 1: $\forall S \subseteq \mathcal{PG}$

$$\sum_{PG_j^f \in S} Ep g_j^f(t) \leq \sum_{PL_\ell^f \in NFL(S) \cup NFL(NS(S))} Ep l_\ell^f(t) + \sum_{PS_h \in NS(S)} (SOC_h^{max} - SOC_h(0)) \cdot \frac{Ess_h}{\eta} \quad (1)$$

Condition 2: $\forall T \subseteq \mathcal{PL}$

$$\sum_{PG_j^f \in NFG(T) \cup NFG(NS(T))} Ep g_j^f(t) \geq \sum_{PL_\ell^f \in T} Ep l_\ell^f(t) + \sum_{PS_h \in NS(T)} (SOC_h^{min} - SOC_h(0)) \cdot \frac{Ess_h}{\eta} \quad (2)$$

For details of mathematical notations, please refer to [3].

D. Linear Programming (LP)

LP optimizes a linear objective function subject to linear equality and inequality constraints. It is a powerful tool in various fields for solving resource allocation problems.

- **Problem Formulation:** Define the objective function, constraints, and variables.
- **Feasibility Check:** Determine if a feasible solution exists.
- **Simplex Method:** Apply the simplex method (or other suitable algorithms) to find the optimal solution.
- **Iterative Process:** Move along the edges of the feasible region to find the best value.
- **Solution Interpretation:** Analyze the final solution and interpret it in the original problem context.

The problem is formulated as:

$$\text{Minimize: } \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } A\mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{x} \geq \mathbf{0} \quad (5)$$

E. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

PSO optimizes a problem by iteratively improving a candidate solution about a given quality measure. It moves a population of candidate solutions, called particles, in the search space to find the optimal solution. PSO optimizes a problem by iteratively trying to improve a candidate solution.

- **Initialization:** Initialize a swarm of particles with random positions and velocities.
- **Velocity Update:** Update each particle's velocity based on its own experience and that of its neighbors.
- **Position Update:** Update each particle's position based on its new velocity.
- **Fitness Evaluation:** Evaluate the fitness of each particle.
- **Repeat:** Repeat the process until an optimal solution is found or a stopping criterion is met.

The updated formulas are:

$$v_i(t+1) = w \cdot v_i(t) + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (p_i - x_i(t)) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (g - x_i(t)) \quad (6)$$

$$x_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + v_i(t+1) \quad (7)$$

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

This section establishes an objective function as a minimization problem, aiming to minimize the cost coefficient matrix F . A decision variable vector x represents the sum of power generators and loads. The equality constraints are established for fluctuating power generators and loads, ensuring the generation is consumed completely, and consumption is satisfied fully. The inequality constraints are formulated for controllable power generators and loads, ensuring maximum and minimum limitations are preserved for each power device.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The performance comparison considering the execution time of two optimization techniques, PSO and LP, is investigated in this section. Two simulation results are discussed in this section: (i) analysis of execution time for both optimization techniques and (ii) analysis of execution time with an increased number of power devices.

In Fig. 1, the bar graph shows that LP with an average execution time of 904.88 seconds is higher than PSO which is 20.87 seconds. The shorter execution time of PSO implies

Fig. 1: Execution time analysis for different algorithms.

Fig. 2: Execution time analysis of LP and PSO with increased number of power devices.

higher efficiency and a more straightforward problem-solving approach. Conversely, the execution time of LP shows the computational complexity of the method. Fig. 2 compares the execution time of PSO and LP considering the number of devices increases from 60, 140, and 200. The result shows that the execution time of LP accelerates very fast for more than 200 devices. In summary, it provides a clear comparison of how each optimization technique is affected by increasing the number of devices. The information is beneficial for selecting optimization techniques for scalable systems.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The investigation in this paper revealed that among the optimization techniques evaluated, including Linear Programming (LP) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), PSO is faster with an increased number of power devices. Overall, the results provide a clear visual representation of the comparative efficiencies of these algorithms, which could be a critical factor in selecting an appropriate method for problem-solving in computational tasks that are sensitive to execution time.

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